

Supporting Information

Bioelectrocatalytic CO₂ Reduction by Redox Polymer Wired Carbon Monoxide Dehydrogenase Gas Diffusion Electrodes

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Table S1. Summary of relevant literature reports for bioelectrodes making use of carbon monoxide dehydrogenases or formate dehydrogenases for CO₂ reduction with the enzymes under direct electron transfer or making use of immobilized enzyme and redox mediators.

Enzyme	Electron transfer regime	Gas diffusion electrode	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	Ref.
W-FDH	DET	No	-0.24 ^[d]	4
W-FDH (<i>DvH</i> ^[a])	DET	No	-0.1	5
W-FDH (<i>DvH</i> ^[a])	MET – PANi hydrogel	No	-3.02 ^[d]	6
W-FDH (<i>DvH</i> ^[a])	DET	Yes	-0.33	7
	MET – viologen based redox polymer	Yes	-0.5	
CODH (rec. <i>Rr</i> ^[b])	DET	Yes	-4.2 ^[d]	8
		No	-2.9 ^[d]	
CODH (rec. <i>Rr</i> ^[b])	DET	Yes	-3.2 ^[d]	9
		No	-4.9 ^[d]	
CODH II (<i>Ch</i> ^[c])	MET – BPEI-[CoCp ₂]	Yes	-4.4 -5.5 ^[d]	<i>This work</i>

[a] *DvH*: *Desulfovibrio vulgaris Hildenborough*, [b] *Rr*: *Rhodospirillum rubrum*, [c] *Ch*: *Carboxydotherrmus hydrogenoformans*, [d] Currents obtained from cyclic voltammetry measurements.

Figure S1. Voltammetric characterization of the redox polymer BPEI-[CoCp₂] on a glassy carbon electrode. Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.3), scan rate: 50 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S2. Control measurement displaying the current response of the BPEI-[CoCp₂] polymer without enzyme. The electrode was measured both in the absence (black) and presence (red) of CO₂. Electrolyte: 0.1 M phosphate buffer, scan rate: 5 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S3. Photograph of the electrochemical setup used during gas chromatography measurements.

Figure S4. Gas chromatographic detection for a fully modified enzymatic electrode under turnover conditions. Product profiles measured with the flame ionization detector for the detection of carbon-based species (A) and thermal conductivity detector for H₂ detection (B). C) Amperometric measurement ($E_{app} = -0.79$ V vs. SHE) conducted during product analysis.

Figure S5. Control experiment measuring a gas diffusion electrode modified with BPEI-[CoCp₂] but without enzyme. Response profiles with the flame ionization detector for the detection of carbon-based species (A-F) and thermal conductivity detector for H₂ detection (G-L) while applying different potentials to the electrode. M) Chronoamperometric measurement conducted during product analysis while stepping the potential (V vs. SHE). Gas feed: CO₂. *The CO₂ signal was electronically removed during data acquisition to aid on the visualization of potentially smaller signals.

Figure S6. Voltammetric characterization before (A) and after (B) the long-term measurement shown in Figure 4 (main text). The CVs were recorded in the absence (black) and presence (red) of CO₂ provided at the backside of the modified gas diffusion electrode. Scan rate: 5 mV s⁻¹. Electrolyte: Ar-saturated 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.3).

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